
Plant volatiles from the Brazilian restinga with bactericidal activity against multiresistant bacteria

Voláteis de plantas da restinga brasileira com atividade bactericida contra bactérias multirresistentes

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the bactericidal activity of Myrtaceae foliar volatile compounds against strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PAO-1) and *Burkholderia cenocepacia* (ET-12). Although these bacteria are clinically important to human health, they, along with other bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus agalactiae*), also have a high profile of antimicrobial resistance associated with bovine mastitis. The chemical composition of volatiles found in Myrtaceae foliar volatiles was also characterized. To accomplish this, the essential oil was extracted from dry leaves of *Eugenia astringens*, *Eugenia arenaria* and *Myrrhinum atropurpureum* by hydrodistillation. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by microdilution in broth. Essential oil from *E. astringens* leaf could inhibit growth the five strains by the Agar diffusion method. MIC demonstrated a reduction in bacterial growth by 74% ± 2.8 (*P. aeruginosa*), 78.3% ± 10.5 (*B. cenocepacia*), 87.1% ± 1.4 (*E. coli*), 99% ± 0.02 (*S. aureus*) and 99.9 ± 0.01 (*S. agalactiae*). The terpene α -pinene was detected in all three species, especially *M. atropurpureum* and *E. astringens*. *E. astringens* showed a high content of (*E*)-caryophyllene.

Keywords: Bactericidal activity; Multiresistant bacteria; Essential oils; Myrtaceae

RESUMO

O estudo visou avaliação da atividade bactericida de compostos voláteis das folhas de Myrtaceae contra as cepas de *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PAO-1) e *Burkholderia cenocepacia* (ET-12), de importância clínica em humanos com alto perfil de resistência antimicrobiana e bactérias associadas à mastite bovina (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* e *Streptococcus agalactiae*) e a caracterização da composição química dos voláteis. O óleo essencial foi extraído de folhas secas de *Eugenia astringens*, *Eugenia arenaria* e *Myrrhinum atropurpureum* por hidrodestilação. A concentração inibitória mínima (CIM) foi determinada por microdiluição em caldo. O óleo essencial da folha de *E. astringens* foi capaz de inibir o crescimento das cinco cepas pelo método de difusão em agar. O MIC demonstrou uma redução do crescimento bacteriano em 74% ± 2,8 (*P. aeruginosa*), 78,3% ± 10,5 (*B. cenocepacia*), 87,1% ± 1,4 (*E. coli*), 99% ± 0,02 (*S. aureus*) e 99,9 ± 0,01 (*S. agalactiae*). O α -pineno foi detectado em três espécies, com destaque para *M. atropurpureum* e *E. astringens*. *E. astringens* apresentou alto teor de (*E*)-cariofileno.

Palavras-chave: Atividade bactericida; Bactérias multirresistentes; Óleos essenciais; Myrtaceae

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INTRODUCTION

Many bacteria are known for their resistance to all classes of antimicrobials and for the ease with which they can acquire new resistance mechanisms (Tafur *et al.*, 2008). Non-fermenting Gram-negative bacteria pose a particular difficulty for the healthcare community because they present maximal multidrug resistance (McGowan, 2006; Muntean *et al.*, 2018). In particular, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Burkholderia cenocepacia* stand out as multidrug-resistant bacteria frequently involved in nosocomial infections with a high mortality rate (Gibson *et al.*, 2003; Zaha *et al.*, 2019). In veterinary medicine, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *Streptococcus agalactiae* are etiological agents of bovine mastitis, an intramammary infection (Angeliki *et al.*, 2019). This polymicrobial disease causes considerable economic losses from the reduced quantity and quality of milk, the loss of quarters reserved for lactating cows, the early slaughter of dairy animals, and the high cost of treatment (Heikkilä *et al.*, 2018; Angeliki *et al.*, 2019). The eradication of these bacteria in humans and animals is often unsuccessful, and therapy is generally aimed at decreasing bacterial density (Lutz *et al.*, 2011; Oliver & Murinda, 2012). The increase in bacterial resistance to multiple antimicrobial drugs has spurred the search for new therapeutic alternatives, such as medicinal plants, which represent an important source for obtaining medicines. The antimicrobial activity of plant extracts and metabolites of essential oils of plants has been proven in several studies carried out in countries that have a diversified flora (Holetz *et al.*, 2002; Castro and Firmida, 2011).

Myrtaceae Juss. is the largest family that belongs to the order Myrtales. It comprises 142 genera and includes more than 5,000 species of trees and shrubs, the occurrence of which has been described in tropical and subtropical regions of the world, with particular diversity in South and Central America and Australia (Chase *et al.*, 2016; Wilson *et al.*, 2005). In Brazil, Myrtaceae is one of the ten richest angiosperm families, and about 50% of species are endemic to Brazil. They are important to fauna for their wild berries (Sobral *et al.*, 2015; Silva & Victório 2021). It is a relevant plant family in the Atlantic Forest domain, quite common in restinga areas and found in several biomes (Souza & Morim, 2008; Arruda & Victório, 2011; Defaveri *et al.*, 2011; Victório *et al.*, 2018; Silva & Victório 2021). The presence of oil aromatic compounds is a chemical feature of this family that presents secretory cavities in leaf parenchyma where terpenoids are produced, stored and secreted (Metcalf & Chalk, 1983; Arruda & Victório 2011; Victório *et al.*, 2018). Several Myrtaceae species are used in folk medicine as antidiarrheal, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antirheumatic, anti-inflammatory, and cleansing agents (De Souza *et al.*, 2018). Data revealed that *Eugenia astringens*, “araponga” and “abajiru” are abundant in restingas and display gastro-protective activity by significant inhibition of ulcer formation. Also, the aerial parts are widely used in folk medicine to treat infections, inflammation, diabetes and

parasites (Kneip, 2009; Meyre-Silva *et al.*, 2009; Carneiro *et al.*, 2021). *Eugenia arenaria*, popular names “pintagaí-uma” and “camboi”, and *Myrrhinum atropurpureum*, also known as “pau-ferro”, “carrapato” and “murtilo”, are endemic to the restingas of Rio de Janeiro. Nonetheless, studies on these species are scarce, and few biological activities have been recorded. Therefore, the present study evaluated the chemical profile and antimicrobial activity of volatiles of *E. astringens*, *E. arenaria* and *M. atropurpureum* from restinga environment against strains of *B. cenocepacia*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *S. agalactiae*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant material

Dry leaves of *Eugenia astringens* Cambess (*syn Eugenia rotundifolia* Casar., *Eugenia umbelliflora* O. Berg) (HUNI650), *Eugenia arenaria* Cambess. and *Myrrhinum atropurpureum* Schott (RB 415731) were used to extract essential oils. Leaves of *E. astringens* and *M. atropurpureum* were collected in August 2016 from individuals of the Grumari restinga (23°02'94"S, 43°31'98"W). *E. arenaria* leaves were also collected in August 2016 from the Massambaba restinga (22°55'33"S 42°16'17"W). Both restingas are in Rio de Janeiro state, Brazil. The plants were identified by taxonomist Dr. Marcelo da Costa Souza and deposited at the Herbarium RBR (UFRRJ). Permission for collection was obtained from the Ministry of the Environment (SISBIO/ICMBio, under number 37376-2).

Distillation and analysis of volatiles

Once collected, the plant materials were oven dried for 3–5 days at 50°C, ground, and stored in the dark at room temperature. Samples between 50 g and 100 g of dry leaves were cut and used in the distillation of essential oils in a Clevenger-type apparatus during 3 h. Pure essential oils were diluted in dichloromethane in the proportion of 1%, and then 1.0 µL of the solution was injected (split 1:20) into an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (GC/FID) and a HP-5MS (5% phenyl-methylpolysiloxane) fused silica capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm). Hydrogen was used as carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/minute. Oven temperature was programmed from 60 to 240°C at 3°C/minute. Injector temperature was kept at 250°C and detector temperature at 280°C. The percentage composition was obtained by normalization. The data presented are the mean of three replicates. Analyses by GC/MS were performed on an Agilent 5973N mass selective detector coupled to an Agilent 6890N gas chromatograph fitted with a HP-5MS fused silica capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm). Helium was used as carrier gas at 1.0 mL/minute. The mass detector was operated in electronic ionization mode (70 eV) at 3.15 scans/second, with mass range from 40 to 450 u. The transfer line was kept at 260°C, ion source at 230°C and analyzer at 150°C. Oven temperature program and injection procedure were the same as noted above. Identification of oil components was

performed by comparing their mass spectra with those from the Wiley Registry of Mass Spectral Data (Wiley, 1994) and by comparing their linear retention indices (LRI) with those from the literature (Adams 2007). LRI were calculated according to Van Den Dool and Kratz (1963) after the injection of a homologous series of hydrocarbons (n -C₇-C₂₆) in the same column and conditions as above.

Bacterial strains used in bactericidal assays

The bacterial strains used for screening were kindly provided by the Collection of Reference Microorganisms in Sanitary Surveillance - FIOCRUZ-INCQS, Rio de Janeiro, RJ: *Escherichia coli* - INCQS (00219) - ATCC (8739), *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp.*aureus*-INCQS (00039) -ATCC (6538) and *Streptococcus agalactiae* - INCQS (00128) -ATCC (13813). The *Burkholderiaceenocepacia* ET-12 strain (sample J2315 belonging to genovariante IIIa) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain PAO-1 were assigned by the Department of Microbiology, Immunology and Parasitology of the Univesidade Estadual do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ).

Preparation of bacterial suspensions

The bacterial suspensions were prepared in Mueller Hinton II medium (MHII). The cultures were homogenized and placed in an orbital shaker - New Ethics) at 150 rpm at 33°C for 18 h. After this time, the cultures were centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatants were discarded, and the pellet formed was homogenized. Dilutions in MHII medium from the bacterial pellet that were performed on a photochrometer (Biochrom, model Libra S2) at 680 nm in order to obtain bacterial suspensions with $DO_{680nm} = 1.3$ which corresponds to 1×10^8 CFU/mL.

Determination of the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of essential oils against Gram-negative and -positive bacteria

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of essential oils was determined by disk diffusion in agar and broth microdilution, according to the standards of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (Wayne, 2012).

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as means \pm SEM of the values obtained. Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 5 software. Statistical differences between groups were determined by Bonferroni's Multiple Comparison Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of bactericidal activity of essential oils by the disk diffusion test

Antibacterial activity of leaf volatiles was evaluated against Gram-positive and -negative bacteria. Results from the disk diffusion test against the different strains showed that the essential oils of *M. atropurpureum* (50%) and *E. arenaria* (25%) had bactericidal activity only for PAO-1 and ET-12, but no activity against the other strains tested. We observed a greater effect on the bactericidal activity of *E. astringens* leaf volatiles, which could significantly inhibit the bacterial growth of all five strains at a minimum concentration of 25% when compared to the growth of cultures not treated with oils (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of leaf volatiles from *Myrtaceae* species, using the disk diffusion test.

Plant species	Minimum inhibitory concentration of leaf oils (vol/vol)				
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ^a	<i>B. cenocepacia</i> ^a	<i>E. coli</i> -	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. agalactiae</i>
<i>E. arenaria</i>	25%	25%	NA*	NA*	NA*
<i>E. astringens</i>	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
<i>M. atropurpureum</i>	50%	50%	NA*	NA*	NA*

*NA- No activity ^aSuccar *et al.* 2019

The disk diffusion technique is one of the cheapest and least labor-intensive antibacterial susceptibility testing methods currently available. However, in the study by Vambe *et al.* (2018), they report that this procedure has difficulties in providing reproducible results for various plant extracts. This can be attributed to the occurrence of some phytochemicals, especially those that are nonpolar, by failing to diffuse rapidly in polarized agarose gels (Rios *et al.*, 1988). When using the agar diffusion technique, other authors report that irregular diffusion of the lipophilic components of essential oils can occur, resulting in uneven concentrations in agar and causing the formation of regions with variable antimicrobial activity (Setzer *et al.*, 2004; Sokmen *et al.*, 2004;). In order to confirm our results, we evaluated bactericidal activity using the microdilution test (MIC).

Determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of essential oils from *Myrtaceae* species against multiresistant strains

The determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration was carried out only with *E. astringens* essential oil by the broth microdilution methodology (Table 2).

Table 2. Bactericidal properties of *Eugenia astringens* leaf volatiles

Bacterial strain	MIC (CFU/mL)	
	Control	25%
<i>Pseudomona aeruginosa</i>	2.1 x10 ⁹ ±0.3	4.5 x10 ⁸ ±1.5**
<i>Burkholderiacenocepacia</i>	1.0 x10 ¹¹ ±0.1	3.5 x10 ⁸ ±0.3**
<i>Echerichia coli</i>	2.9 x10 ⁹ ±0.9	2.2 x10 ⁸ ±0.2*
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	2.5 x10 ⁸ ±0.5	8.3 x10 ³ ±4.2***
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.4 x10 ⁷ ±0.8	1.7 x10 ³ ±1.3***

MIC= Minimum inhibitory concentration (vol/vol%), CFU/mL= Colony Forming Units/mL. The results represent mean ± SEM of three experiments performed in triplicate. *p< 0.05, **p<0.01 and *** p<0.001 were obtained after comparison with untreated control.

P. aeruginosa and *B. cenocepacia* showed more resistance to treatment with the essential oil of *E. astringens* when compared to the other strains tested. These data are in agreement with those found in the literature, which report the greater tolerance of *Pseudomonas* sp. to inhibition of bacterial growth compared to other species by essential oils of plants (Raut & Karuppaiyl, 2014).

To better demonstrate the inhibitory action of *E. astringens* essential oil, **Figure 1** gives the percentage of growth inhibition of bacterial cultures treated with 25% essential oil when compared to untreated cultures taken as 100%.

Reductions of 74% (*P. aeruginosa*), 78.3% (*B. cenocepacia*), 87.1% (*E. coli*), 99% (*S. aureus*) and 99.9% (*S. agalactiae*) of bacterial mass were observed in cultures of the five strains treated with essential oils. The treatment was more efficient for Gram-positive strains, reducing bacterial growth by 90%. These data were in agreement with several other reports where essential oils were shown to be more active towards Gram-positive than Gram-negative bacteria (Marino *et al.*, 2002; Chorianopoulos *et al.*, 2004; Gutierrez *et al.*, 2008; Tiwari *et al.*, 2009). Gram-negative bacteria are less susceptible to the action of antibacterials because they have an outer membrane that consists of phospholipids, proteins, and lipopolysaccharides (LPS), limiting the diffusion of hydrophobic compounds across the plasma membrane (Burt, 2004; Bassolé & Juliani, 2012). Since essential oils are typically lipophilic, they can accumulate in the lipid bilayer. This accumulation of lipids in the outer membrane of the bacterial cell reduces its diffusion and insertion into the inner membrane.

Figure 1. Percentage of inhibition of bacterial growth under *Eugenia astringens* leaf volatiles. The results represent mean \pm SEM of three experiments performed in triplicate

The affinity of essential oils for lipid compounds in the bacterial inner membrane causes structural changes making it more permeable to protons and ions. Therefore, damage to the membrane causes functional changes, such as selective permeability, enzymatic activity and energy generation promoted by the decrease of proton force (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008).

Phytochemical analysis of leaf oils

Hydrodistillation of the dry leaves of *E. astringens*, *E. arenaria* and *M. atropurpureum* gave essential oils in yields of 2.06 ± 0.25 , 5.85 ± 0.85 and 4.03 ± 0.67 $\mu\text{L/g}$, respectively.

Figure 4 compares the main components of leaf volatiles from Myrtaceae species used in the agar disk diffusion method. **Table 3** presents the chemical composition of leaf volatiles identified in *E. astringens* and used in continuous testing to evaluate bactericidal activity.

The sesquiterpenes represented the main fraction of leaf volatiles of *E. astringens* accounting for 51.1%, as characterized by a high percentage of oxygenated monoterpenes. *M. atropurpureum* species were mainly composed of monoterpenes (76.7%), the most abundant among them being α -pinene (35.5%), 1,8 cineol (20.8), and (24.8%) of sesquiterpenes. *E. arenaria* essential oil was rich in sesquiterpenes, including (*E*)-caryophyllene, α -muurolene, caryophyllene oxide, 1,10-di-epi-cubenol and apodophyllene, the main component in oils.

Studies by Victorio *et al.* (2011) for the species *M. atropurpureum* showed proportions similar those those noted above between mono- (80%) and sesquiterpenes (17%), although the collection was carried out in April, 2009, a time of year characterized by different climatic events in Brazil. The representativeness of the components was the same in that α -pinene and 1,8 cineole were the main monoterpenes, considering the relative area.

Figure 4. The major leaf volatiles: mono- and sesquiterpenes from leaves of *Eugenia astringens*, *E. arenaria* and *Myrrhinium atropurpureum* collected in Brazilian restingas

Previous studies have gathered data for the analysis of *E. astringens* volatiles (Magina *et al.* 2009; Defaveri *et al.* 2011; De Souza *et al.* 2018). In the present report, we highlight the presence of the major components α - and β -pinenes (**Figure 4**) in accordance with *E. astringens* oils from leaves collected in October in Santa Catarina, southern Brazil, although the amount is much smaller, 11.2 and 13.2% (Magina *et al.* 2009). In comparison with *M. atropurpureum* volatiles, the same α -pinene component was found in large amounts. The difference really lies in

the concentration of β -pinene, which is about 22% higher in *E. astringens*, and the presence of high concentrations (20.8%) of 1,8-cineole in *M. atropurpureum*. Among *E. astringens* volatiles, this study highlights the presence of glenol+globulol (14.6%) and volatiles from the selinene group, such as selin-11-en-4 α -ol (5.3%) (**Table 3**).

Unlike *E. astringens* and *M. atropurpureum*, *E. arenaria* showed concentrations of α - and β -pinenes and 1.8 cineol below 8%, while in the set of volatiles of *E. arenaria*, α -pinene (7.9%) stands out. *E. astringens* and *E. arenaria* have similar concentrations of (*E*)-caryophyllene (8.8% and 8.3%, respectively), and all evaluated species have close values of caryophyllene oxide (*E. arenaria* – 10.2%, *E. astringens* - 7.3, and *M. atropurpureum* – 7.9%) (**Figure 4**).

Based on other studies of antimicrobial activity with volatiles from Myrtaceae species, the most promising essential oils contain such components as α -pinene, 1,8-cineole, α -terpineol, and β -caryophyllene that show strong antimicrobial properties and are commonly cited (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008; Hyun-Jun & Su-Kyun, 2018; Allenspach & Steuer, 2021; Santos *et al.*, 2021). Among the essential oils studied, the set of volatiles from *E. astringens* had better bactericidal responses, with (*E*)-caryophyllene and α -pinene being the volatile components in greatest quantities (**Figure 4**). However, synergistic activity between the phytochemicals of essential oils is generally responsible for the biological activity, not necessarily the most abundant component.

Table 3. Chemical composition of volatiles of leaves of *Eugenia astringens* collected in Grumari restinga, Brazil.

Compounds	LRI exp ^a	Relative area (%)
		<i>E. astringens</i>
α -thujene	927	0.2
α -pinene	934	23.6
n.i.	942	0.4
camphene	948	0.3
β -pinene	976	31.1
myrcene	991	0.4
limonene	1027	1.6
1,8-cineol	1029	0.2
γ -terpinene	1057	0.2
terpinolene	1088	0.3
<i>endo</i> -fenchol	1113	0.1
camphene hydrate	1146	0.1
borneol	1164	0.1
terpinen-4-ol	1176	0.2
α -terpineol	1190	2.6
bornyl acetate	1285	0.1
<i>trans</i> -pinocarvylacetate	1299	5.7
α -cubebene	1348	0.5
α -copaene	1374	0.4
α -gurjunene	1407	0.72
(<i>E</i>)-caryophyllene	1417	8.8
β -gurjunene	1429	0.3
aromadendrene	1446	2.2
<i>trans</i> -muurola-3,5-diene	1448	0.4

α -humulene	1451	1.1
<i>allo</i> -aromadendrene	1458	0.8
<i>trans</i> -cadin-1(6),4-diene	1471	0.6
β -selinene	1483	2.1
valencene	1485	0.2
α -selinene	1492	0.4
γ -cadinene	1513	0.7
<i>trans</i> -calamenene +zoarene	1521	5.7
<i>trans</i> -cadi-1,4-diene	1530	1.6
n.i.	1557	1.2
spathulenol	1577	5.6
caryophyllene oxide	1580	7.2
glenol+globulol	1581	14.6
viridiflorol	1590	0.7
cubeban-11-ol	1591	0.2
rosifoliol	1600	1.4
humulene epoxide II	1607	0.2
n.i.	1611	0.5
1,10-di- <i>epi</i> -cubenol	1614	0.4
n.i.	1621	0.5
1- <i>epi</i> -cubenol	1626	4.6
n.i.	1631	0.6
cariofila-4(12),8(13)dien-5 α or 5 β -ol	1635	1.4
<i>epi</i> - α -cadinol + <i>epi</i> - α -muurolol	1641	3.7
α -muurolol	1646	0.7
n.i.	1650	0.1
selin-11-en-4 α -ol	1653	5.3
<i>neo</i> -intermedeol	1656	0.4
n.i.	1668	0.5
muskatone	1676	0.1
n.i.	1677	0.5
apodophyllene	1709	0.9
n.i.	1767	0.2
Monoterpenes		32.7
Diterpenes		5.8
Sesquiterpenes		51.1
<i>Yield</i> (μ L/g) ^b		2.06 \pm 0.25

^aLRlexp: experimental linear retention indices (calculated according to Van den Dool & Kratz 1963).

^bSuccar *et al.* 2019, n= 3. Values show media from 3 analyses and 3 injections. *The results represent means \pm standard error of the phytochemical analysis of three samples of essential oils. **n.i. - no identified.

CONCLUSION

Data showed that most antimicrobial activity of the tested volatile oils appears to derive from terpenoids, particularly monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes. A bioautography study would be necessary to confirm the volatile compounds involved in the antimicrobial action. Results found using *E. astringens* leaf volatiles demonstrated the potential to exert beneficial antibacterial effect and could be a natural source, especially when used in combination with antibiotics to enhance their activity. However, further studies are in order to determine their mode of action and probable toxicological effects in order to optimize their use.

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REFERÊNCIAS

- ADAMS, R. P. **Identification of Essential Oil Components by Gas Chromatography/ Mass Spectrometry**. 4th ed. Carol Stream, IL: Allured Publishing Corporation, 804p. 2007.
- ALLENSPACH, C.; STEUER, C. α -Pinene: a never-ending story. **Phytochemistry**, v.190, p.112857, 2021. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2021.112857.
- ANGELIKI, A.; HOLOHAN, R.; REA, M. C.; WARDA, A. K.; HILL, C., ROSS, R. P. Bovine mastitis is a polymicrobial disease requiring a polydiagnostic approach. **International Dairy Journal**, v.99, p.104539, 2019. Disponível: doi:10.1016/j.idairyj.2019.104539.
- ARRUDA, R. C. O.; VICTÓRIO, C. P. Leaf secretory structure and volatile compounds of *Eugenia copacabanensis* Kiaersk. (Myrtaceae). **Journal of Essential Oil Research**, v.23, p. 1-5, 2011. Disponível: doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2011.9700472.
- BAKKALI, F.; AVERBECK, S.; AVERBECK, D.; IDAOMAR, M. Biological effects of essential oils – A review. **Food and Chemical Toxicology**, v. 46, p.446–475, 2008. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2007.09.106 .
- BASSOLÉ, I. H. N.; JULIANI, H. R. Essential Oils in Combination and Their Antimicrobial Properties. **Molecules**, v.17, p.3989-4006; 2012. Disponível: doi:10.3390/molecules17043989
- BURT, S. Essential oils: their antibacterial properties and potential applications in foods—a review. **International Journal of Food Microbiology**, v. 94, p. 223-253, 2004. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2004.03.022.
- CARNEIRO, V. C. S.; LUCENA, L. A.; FIGUEIRÓ, R.; VICTÓRIO, C. P. Larvicidal activity of plants from Myrtaceae against *Aedes aegypti* L. and *Simulium pertinax* Kollar (Diptera). **Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical**, v.54, p. 1-8, 2021. Disponível: doi.org/10.1590/0037-8682-0092-2020.
- CASTRO, M.C.S.; FIRMIDA, M. C. O tratamento da fibrose cística e suas complicações. **Revista do HUPE-UERJ**, v. 10, p. 82-108, 2011.
- CHASE, M.W.;CHRISTENHUSZ, M. J. M.; FAY, M. F.; BYNG, W S.; JUDD,D.E.S.; MABERLEY, D.J.; SENNIKOV, A.N.; SOLTIS, P.S.; STEVENS, P.F.An update of the Angiosperm PhylogenyGroup, classification for the orders and families of flowering plants: APG IV. Botanical. **Journal of the Linnean Society**, v.18: p.1-20, 2016. Disponível: doi.org/10.1111/boj.12385.
- CHORIANOPOULOS, N.; KALPOUTZAKIS, E.; ALIGIANNIS, N.; MITAKU, S.; NYCHAS, G.J.; HAROUTOUNIAN, S.A. Essential oils of *Satureja*, *Origanum*, and *Thymus* species: Chemical composition and antibacterial activities against foodborne pathogens. **Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry**, v.52, p. 8261-8267, 2004. Disponível: doi.org/10.1021/jf049113i.

DE SOUZA, A.; DE OLIVEIRA, C.; DE OLIVEIRA, V.; BETIM, F.; MIGUEL, O.; MIGUEL, M. Traditional uses, phytochemistry, and antimicrobial activities of *Eugenia* Species – A Review. **Planta Medica**, v. 84, p. 1232-1248, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1055/a-0656-7262

DEFAVERI, A. C. A.; SATO, ALICE.; BORRÉ, L. B.; AGUIAR, D. L. M. GIL.; SAN, R. A. S.; ARRUDA, R. C. O.; RIEHL, C. A. S. *Eugenia neonitida* Sobral and *Eugenia rotundifolia* Casar. (Myrtaceae) essential oils: composition, seasonality influence, antioxidant activity and leaf histochemistry. **Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society**, v. 22(8), p. 1531-1538, 2011. Disponível: doi.org/10.1590/S0103-50532011000800018.

GIBSON, R. L.; BURNS, J. L.; RAMSEY, B. W. Pathophysiology and management of pulmonary infections in cystic fibrosis. **American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine**, Nova York, v.168, n.8, p.918–951, 2003

GUTIERREZ, J.; RODRIGUEZ, G.; BARRY-RYAN, C.; BOURKE, P. Efficacy of plant essential oils against foodborne pathogens and spoilage bacteria associated with ready-to-eat vegetables: Antimicrobial and sensory screening. **Journal of Food Protection**, v.71, p.1846-1854, 2008. Disponível: doi.org/10.4315/0362-028x-71.9.1846.

HEIKKILÄ, A. M.; LISKI, E.; PYÖRÄLÄ, S.; TAPONEN, S. Pathogen-specific production losses in bovine mastitis. **Journal of Dairy Science**, v. 101, p.9493-9504, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14824.

HOLETZ, F. B. *et al.* Screening of some plants used in the Brazilian folkmedicine for the treatment of infectious diseases. **Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz**, v. 97, p.1027-1031, 2002. Disponível: doi.org/10.1590/S0074-02762002000700017.

HYUN-JUN, Y.; SU-KYUN J. Inhibitory effects of β -caryophyllene on *Streptococcus mutans* biofilm. **Archives of Oral Biology**, v.88, p.42-46, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.archoralbio.2018.01.009.

KNEIP, L. M. A utilização de plantas pelos pescadores, coletores e caçadores pré-históricos da restinga de Saquarema, Rio de Janeiro, Brasil. **Rodriguésia**, v.60, p. 203-210. 2009. Disponível: doi.org/10.1590/2175-7860200960111.

LUTZ, L.; DE-PARIS, F.; VIEIRA, M. I.; MARQUES, E. A.; BARTH, A. L. Bacteriologia da fibrose cística. **Revista HCPA**, Porto Alegre, v. 31, p. 168-184, 2011.

MAGINA, M. D. A.; DALMARCO, E. M.; WISNIEWSKI, A.; SIMIONATTO, E. L.; DALMARCO, J. B.; PIZZOLATTI, M. G.; BRIGHENTE, I. M. C. Chemical composition and antibacterial activity of essential oils of *Eugenia* species. **Journal of Natural Medicines**, v. 63, p. 345–350, 2009. Disponível: doi.org/10.1007/s11418-009-0329-5.

MARINO, I. R.; PANARELLO, G.; SINGH, N. Efficacy of *Aspergillus* galactomannan-directed preemptive therapy for the prevention of invasive aspergillosis

in organ transplant recipients. **Transplant Infectious Disease**, v. 4, p. 226-227, 2002. Disponível: doi.org/10.1034/j.1399-3062.2002.02003.x

MCGOWAN JR, J.E. Resistance in nonfermenting Gram-negative bacteria: multidrug resistance to the maximum. **American Journal of Medicine**, v.119, p. 29-36; 2006. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2006.03.014.

METCALFE, C. R.; CHALK, L. **Anatomy of the Dicotyledons, Vol. 2. Wood structure and conclusion of the general introduction**. Clarendon Press, Oxford, 2nd Ed. , p. 64- 67, 1983.

MEYRE-SILVA, C.; PETRY, C. M.; BERTÉ, T. E.; BECKER, R. G.; ZANATTA, F.; DELLE-MONACHE, F.; CECHINEL-FILHO, V.; ANDRADE, S. F. Phytochemical analyses and gastroprotective effects of *Eugenia umbelliflora* (Myrtaceae) on experimental gastric ulcers. **Natural Product Communications**, v.4 (7), p.911-916,2009. Disponível: doi.org/10.1177/1934578X0900400706

MUNTEAN, D.; HORHAT, F-G.; BĂDITOIU, L.; DUMITRAS, V.; BAGIU J-C.; HORHAT, D-I.; COSNITĂ, D. A.; KRASTA, A.; DUGĂE, D.; LICKER, M. Multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacilli: a retrospective study of trends in a tertiary Healthcare Unit. **Medicina (Kaunas)**, v. 54, p.92, 2018. Disponível: doi:10.3390/medicina54060092

OLIVER, S. P.; MURINDA, S. E. Antimicrobial resistance of mastitis pathogens. **Veterinary Clinics of North America: Food Animal Practice**, v. 28, no.2, p. 165–185, 2012. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.cvfa.2012.03.005

RAUT, J. S.; KARUPPAYIL, S. M. Bioprospecting of plant essential oils for medicinal uses. In: Fulekar, M.H., Pathak, B., Kale, R.K. (Eds.), **Environment and Sustainable Development**. Springer, India, p. 59–76, 2014. Disponível: doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-1166-2_5.

RIOS, J.; RECIO, M.; VILLAR, A. Screening methods for natural products with antimicrobial activity: a review of the literature. **Journal of Ethnopharmacology**, v.23, p.127–149, 1988. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741(88)90001-3.

SANTOS, E. L.; FREITAS, P. R.; ARAÚJO A.C.J. *et al.* Enhanced antibacterial effect of antibiotics by the essential oil of *Aloysia gratissima* (Gillies & Hook.) Tronc. and its major constituent beta-caryophyllene. **Phytomedicine Plus**, v. 1, p.100100, 2021. Disponível; doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2021.100100.

SETZER, W. N.; VOGLER, B.; SCHMIDT, J. M.; LEAHY, J.G.; RIVES, R.. Antimicrobial activity of *Artemisia douglasiana* leaf essential oil. **Fitoterapia**, v.75: p.192-200, 2004. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2003.12.019.

SILVA, L. T. M.; VICTÓRIO, C. P. Green areas in the West Zone of Rio de Janeiro: the environmental heritage of Atlantic Forest. **Meio ambiente (Brasil)**, v.3 (1), p.112–136. 2021. Disponível: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558577

- SOBRAL, M.; PROENÇA, C.; SOUZA, M. et al. Myrtaceae in Lista de Espécies da Flora do Brasil. Jardim Botânico do Rio de Janeiro. 2015. Disponível em: <<http://floradobrasil.jbrj.gov.br/jabot/floradobrasil/FB171>>.
- SOKMEN, A.; GULLUCE, M.; AKPULAT, H.A.; DAFERERA, D.; TEPE, B.; POLISSIOU, M.; SOKMEN, M.; SAHIN, F. The *in vitro* antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of the essential oils and methanol extracts of endemic *Thymus spathulifolius*. **Food Control**, v.15 (8), p. 627-634, 2004. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2003.10.005
- SOUZA, A.; M., OLIVEIRA, C. F.; OLIVEIRA, V. B.; BETIM, F. C. M., MIGUEL, O. G.; MIGUEL, M. D. Traditional uses, phytochemistry, and antimicrobial activities of *Eugenia* species – a review. **Planta Medica**, v. 84, p.1232–1248, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1055/a-0656-7262
- SOUZA, M. C.; MORIM, M. P. Subtribes Eugeniinae O. Berg and Myrtinae O. Berg (Myrtaceae) at Marambaia Restinga, Rio de Janeiro State, Brazil. **Acta Botanica Brasilica**, v.22, p.652, 2008. Disponível: doi.org/10.1590/S0102-33062008000300006
- SUCCAR, J. B.; PINTO, G. M.; PEREIRA, T. F.; DIREITO, I. C. N.; ASSIS, M. C.; VICTÓRIO, C. P. Atividade antibacteriana de óleos essenciais de plantas de Myrtaceae contra bactérias multiresistentes. In: Oliveira Júnior JMB. **Análise Crítica das Ciências Biológicas e da Natureza 2**. Editora Atena. p. 181, 2019. Disponível: DOI [10.22533/at.ed.58319270517](https://doi.org/10.22533/at.ed.58319270517).
- TAFUR, J. D.; TORRES, J. A.; VILLEGAS, M. V. Mecanismos de resistencia a los antibióticos en bacterias Gram negativas. **Infectio**, Bogotá, v.12, p.218-219, 2008.
- TIWARI, B.K.; VALDRAMIDIS, V.P.; O'DONNELL, C.P.; MUTHUKUMARAPPAN, K.; BOURKE, P.; CULLEN, P.J. Application of natural antimicrobials for food preservation. **Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry**, v.57, p.5987-6000, 2009. Disponível: doi.org/10.1021/jf900668n.
- VAMBÉ, M.; AREMU, A. O.; CHUKWUJEKWU, J. C.; FINNIE, J.F.; STADEN, J. V. Antibacterial screening, synergy studies and phenolic content of seven South African medicinal plants against drug-sensitive and –resistant microbial strains. **South African Journal of Botany**, v. 114, p. 250–259, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2017.11.011
- VAN DEN DOOL, H.; KRATZ, P. D. J. A Generalization of the retention index system including linear temperature programmed gas-liquid partition chromatography. **Journal of Chromatography**, v. 11, p. 463-471, 1963. Disponível: [doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(01\)80947-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)80947-X)
- VICTÓRIO, C. P.; AZEVEDO, A. C.; SILVEIRA, E. G. P. *et al.* Leaf essential oils and volatiles, histochemistry and micromorphology of *Neomitranthes obscura* (DC.) N. Silveira (Myrtaceae) growing in sandy coastal plains of Rio de Janeiro. **Biochemical Systematics and Ecology**, v. 78, p.66-76, 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.bse.2018.03.010

VICTÓRIO, C. P.; MOREIRA, C. B.; SOUZA, M. C. *et al.* Secretory cavities and volatiles of *Myrrhinium atropurpureum* Schott var. *atropurpureum* (Myrtaceae): an endemic species collected in the restingas of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. **Natural Product Communications**, v.6 (7), p.1045-1050, 2011. Disponível: doi.org/10.1177/1934578X1100600730

WAYNE, P.A. Methods for Dilution Antimicrobial Susceptibility Tests for Bacteria That Grow Aerobically; Approved Standard—Ninth Edition. **CLSI document M07-A9**: *Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute*; 2012.

WILEY REGISTRY OF MASS SPECTRAL DATA, 6th edn. Wiley Interscience, New York, 1994.

WILSON, P.G.; O'BRIEN, M.M.; HESLEWOOD, M.M.; QUINN, C.J. Relationships within Myrtaceae sensu lato based on a matK phylogeny. **Plant Systematics and Evolution**, v. 251, p. 3-19. 2005. Disponível: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00606-004-0162-y>.

ZAHA, D. C., KISS, R.; HEGED, C.; GESZTELYI, R.; BOMBICZ, M.; MURESAN, M.; PALLAG, A.; ZRINYI, M.; PALL, D.; VESA, C. M.; MICLE, O. Recent Advances in Investigation, Prevention, and Management of Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs): Resistant Multidrug Strain Colonization and Its Risk Factors in an Intensive Care Unit of a University Hospital. **BioMed Research International**, v. 9, p.66-76. 2018. Disponível: doi.org/10.1016/j.bse.2018.03.010.

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